

INDUCED MORPHOLOGICAL MUTANTS IN *CAJANUS CAJAN* (L.) MILLSP

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Abstract: Two Pigeon pea (*Cajanus cajan* (L.) Millspaugh varieties are treated with γ – rays and EMS at different doses in alone and in combination. Frequency and types of morphological variants and mutants are studied in M₁ and M₂ generations and the observed mutant plants have been described. A wide spectrum of morphological mutants obtained in M₂ like Unifoliate leaf, Linear leaf, Tiny leaf, Variable number of leaflets, Multifoliate leaf, Prostrate, Dwarf, Late flowering, Early maturity Grain coat colour, etc. confirms strong Mutagenicity of γ - rays and EMS and that the dose or concentration used in the present investigation are effective. The most frequent mutants were those affecting leaf form (Leaf form mutations) in which two leaf mutants are particularly interesting i.e. Unifoliate mutant from the EMS and Multifoliate from the γ – rays treatment. The former is semifertile but very vigorous, unlike the weak later mutant.. The increasing doses of mutagens in both the varieties were found to be more effective as they induce higher frequency of viable Morphological mutants in M₂ generation. The variety ICPL 93117 is more sensitive to both the Mutagens than ICPL 93115. The treatment dose of 35 Kr appeared to be most effective in inducing mutations in Pigeon pea. The results revealed Radiosensitivity corresponded positively with Chemo-sensitivity in both the varieties and their mutability and also revealed the existence of a Parallelism.

Key words: Pigeon pea, Induced morphological mutants, γ – rays, EMS, Red gram

I. Introduction

Pigeon pea (*Cajanus cajan* (L.) Millspaugh is an important Pulse crop in Semi-Arid Tropics and serves as a major protein source in the daily diet of the people. Various studies [1-6] have reported a number of morphological mutants of spontaneous as well as induced in this crop plant. Most of these Mutants were particularly Leaf form or Habitual ones, however, have been lost during the course of time.

Keeping in view the fact that induction of mutations is an important tool in conferring specific attributes to improved genotypes; preliminary studies were made on mutagenic effects in Pigeon pea. Therefore, mutagen treatments were planned using two Pigeon pea cultivars for isolating true breeding mutants of Agronomic importance especially for disease and insect resistance, high yielding and early maturing through mutational change by increasing variability with least alternation in the rest of the genome. Combination treatments with these mutagens were attempted with the objective of further increasing the mutation frequency and spectra on one hand, and to assess the relative mutagenicity of these agents on the other to select an efficient mutagen for inducing variation. To study the relative response of the two determinate varieties towards the mutagens used and to know the relative mutagenicity and also the optimum dosages of the two Mutagens is the objective of this paper by recording the Mutagen-induced mutations.

2. Materials and Methods

The seeds of two diploid Pigeon pea cultivars obtained from Genetic Resource Unit ICRISAT, Hyderabad, India were used for mutagen treatments. The two mutagens used for seed treatment were EMS and γ – rays. Solutions of EMS were prepared in Phosphate buffer, P^H 7.4 and γ – rays were given in Gamma – chamber (⁶⁰ Co) available at Andhra University, Visakhapatnam at a dose rate of 5 Kr per minute. Dry seeds were treated with different concentrations of EMS (0.1, 0.2 and 0.3%) for 8 hrs. and of γ – rays (15, 25 and 35 Kr). A Control was also raised using only Phosphate buffer, instead of Mutagen. Chemically treated seeds were washed in running tap water and then sown in field plot. Seeds were collected from the individual M₁ plants and used for raising M₂ progenies.

3. Results

In a total population of about 2000 M₂ plants, 39 Mutant plants were spotted out (Table 2). The mutations occurred in both the varieties under all the γ – rays and EMS treatments but the largest proportion was found in case of ICPL 93115 treated with 35 Kr. In response to Chemical mutagen, the two Pigeon pea cultivars yielded 10 Morphological mutants in M₂ segregating families. The different Mutants obtained in M₂ generation and their frequency is presented in Table 1. A total of 10 Morphological mutant types could be detected right from the seedling stage of M₂ generation. The mutants were obtained from both Physical and Chemical mutagen in separate as well as in combination treatments. A brief description of the isolated Mutants along with their genetic behaviour is given below.

Leaf form mutants

1. **Unifoliate leaf:** One mutant from 0.2% EMS treatment of ICPL 93115 was peculiar in possessing Unifoliate leaves contrary to the Trifoliate compound leaves of Pigeon pea (Fig 1.a.). Close examination revealed the complete absence of the two lateral leaflets which are represented by minute stipel like structures on either side of the existing middle leaflet having its own stipels. This was similar to the Simple leaf mutant reported [1,2,7,8].
2. **Linear leaf:** Four seedlings from 0.2 % EMS treatment of ICPL 93117 were distinct from the rest of the population right from the cotyledonary leaf stage itself in having narrow shape of the middle as well as the lateral leaflets. The petioles were shorter than those of the normal leaves. All the leaves borne out by the plant were of the same mutant morphology. The plants survived throughout the growing season but did not flowered (Fig 1.b.).
3. **Multifoliate leaf:** In the case of 0.3 % concentration of EMS treatment of ICPL 93117 variety, 5 of the seedlings were characteristic in having more number of leaflets per leaf instead of the normal trifoliate compound leaf (Fig.1.c.). The number of leaflets was 4 or 5 with irregular margin in all the leaflets. The mutant trait could be consistently seen throughout the growing season. The plants were late in maturity, scanty flowering with high pollen sterility ranging from 60-70 % and no seed set could be obtained for studying the inheritance pattern of this mutant type.

4. Variable number of leaflets: Two mutant plants from 25 Kr dose of γ -rays irradiation of ICPL 93117 variety are significant. The number of leaflets varied from 1 to 3 in different leaves of the same plants (Fig.1.d). This variation in the leaflet number is consistent throughout the plant growth. However, the mutant plants showed poor growth rate and died before attaining maturity.

Habitual Mutants:

5. Prostrate: Three mutant plants from 35 Kr γ -rays irradiation of ICPL 93115 variety showed slender and much elongated stem right from the seedlings stage, representing Prostrate habit (Fig.1.e). However, the primary branches showed erect habit due to their vertical growth but the leaves borne on the primary branches showed elongated internodes with increased leaf lamina. The mutants flowered late and seed set could not be obtained. This is identical to the prostrate mutant observed in M_2 generation of irradiated material described and recorded earlier [9]. It is earlier in maturity and possesses better fruiting.

6. Tiny: Five plants in the case of 35 Kr γ -rays irradiated population of ICPL 93115 variety showed very poor and stunted growth (Fig.1.f.). The altered Morphology was so striking that they remained in 15-25 leaved stage, while the sister plants of the cultivars were stout at flowering stage. This bears some resemblances with the tiny mutant [9] but differs from it in nature. However, unlike Multifoliate mutant this mutant is of rare occurrence in nature.

7. Dwarf: Three mutants characterized by Dwarf stature were obtained from combined treatment of ICPL 93117 variety. The leaves were quite compactly arranged due to shortened internodes. The mutants showed delayed flowering with 40-50 % pollen sterility and no seed set. A few flowers were formed with very low pollen Fertility. This mutation appears to be similar to the Dwarf mutant reported [9].

Other Mutants:

8. Early flowering: Seven plants flowered early by about 20 days in 35 Kr dose of γ -ray irradiation in ICPL 93115 than the Controls. These mutants were short statured (70-95 cm in height) and matured in 110-120 days compared to 130-140 days of the Controls. The fruiting is somewhat below normal.

9 High yielding: Five plants at 25 Kr dose of γ -ray irradiation of ICPL 93115 were found to be High yielding. The Mean of the number of pods per plant was nearly double (216 per plant) than that of the Control (120). The Mean weight of 100 seeds in the mutant was also more (11.45g) compared to the Control values of 10.66 g in ICPL 93117.

10. Grain colour: The normal colour of the seeds used was reddish brown. Four of the M_2 plants of 15 Kr γ -ray irradiated ICPL 93117 produced white, speckled and spotted seeds.

Some of the mutations induced by mutagens during the present study have also occurred in nature. eg. Unifoliate leaf, Narrow leaf and Sterile mutants. This confirms the general belief that γ -ray, EMS and other mutagenic agents accelerate the appearance of Natural mutations. Out of seven induced morphological mutants, the Simple leaf mutant was found to be highly sterile and the other six show partial sterility. Some of the mutations recorded in this paper like Unifoliate leaf, and Multifoliate mutants do not seem to have been recorded earlier.

A comparative statement showing the differences in respect of a number of morphological characters of these mutants as well the 'Simple leaf' mutant which was obtained by mutagen induced has been presented (Table 2.) It has been previously reported [8] that some of the mutations occasionally throw normal plants in their progenies but no Off-type or Normal plant has ever been observed in the progeny of any of the above Mutants.

TABLE.1. Morphological mutants obtained in M₂ generation

Sl No	Mutant type/Name	No of Mutants obtained	Mutagen/ Origin	Brief Morphological description
1.	Unifoliate leaf	1	EMS 0.2 %	Single middle leaflet with increased lamina size. The two lateral leaflets are reduced
2.	Linear leaflets	4	EMS 0.2 %	Leaflets are narrow, Reduced petiole length
3.	Multifoliate leaf with irregular leaflet margin	5	EMS 0.3 %	Leaflets are 4 to 5 in number at different nodes of the same plant
4.	Variable number of leaflets	2	γ-rays 25 Kr	Leaves with different number of leaflets are present on the same plant at different nodes
5.	Prostrate	3	γ-rays 35 Kr	Stem grows parallel to the soil, Some of the terminal branches are erect
6.	Tiny	5	35 Kr	Poor and stunted growth
7.	Dwarf	3	γ-rays 15 kr+ EMS 0.1 %	Leaves arranged quite compactly due to shortened internodes
8.	Early flowering	7	35 Kr	Mutants came to flowering in about 85 to 95 days after sowing
9.	High yielding/More no. of pods	5	25 Kr	Number of pods per plant was about 216
10.	Seed coat colour variant	4	15 Kr	White speckled and spotted seeds

TABLE 2 Frequency of Morphological mutants obtained in two varieties in M₂ generation at mature plant stage

Treatments		Variety ICPL 93115			Variety ICPL 93117		
Control/ Mutagen	Dose/Conc	Total no. of plants screened	No. of Mutants*	Mutant frequency (%)	Total no. of plants screened	No. of Mutants*	Mutant frequency (%)
Control	-----	274	-	-	281	-	-
γ-rays	15 Kr	386	-	-	395	4	1.013
	25 Kr	364	5	1.370	442	2	0.453
	35 Kr	353	15	4.250	440	-	-
EMS	0.1 %	398	-	-	386	-	-
	0.2 %	407	1	0.246	405	4	0.998
	0.3 %	451	-	-	260	5	1.923
γ-rays + EMS	15 Kr+ 0.1 %	478	-	-	448	3	0.670
Total No. of Mutants obtained			21		18		

*Includes all types of Mutants obtained

Figure 1 a-e. Control and Morphological mutants

4. Discussion

A wide spectrum of morphological mutants observed in M_2 generation of the present study, confirms the strong mutagenicity of EMS and γ - rays and it is important to ascertain their actions at Cellular levels, in view of its potential practical utilization as suggested [9]. Variability observed in M_2 was much more than that observed in M_1 as expected. The Mutant characters such as Dwarf, Late and Early flowering plant types were however found to be not sexually transmissible. Appearance of such deviant types after Chemical treatment is a common observation reported in several Plant genera. From the study of variants induced by Chemical mutagens in *Arabidopsis thaliana*, [10] concluded that, all Mutagens induced genetic variations and shifts in Mean flowering time and Plant height.

Some of the Morphological mutants such as Multifoliate leaf and Prostrate mutants in M_2 were reported for the first time. The other mutants such as Unifoliate leaf, Dwarfs, Early and Late flowering mutants were reported earlier as spontaneous as well as induced. Appearance of Unifoliate leaf mutant in M_2 generation indicates the probable homozygous recessive nature and under the control of a single gene, which probably exert Pleiotropic effect on Pollen as well as Ovule fertilities.

Reduction in Pollen fertility appears not to be necessarily associated with reduced pod and seed set. Different Morphological variants observed in M_1 and M_2 generations especially those affecting the Morphology of Leaves and Plant habit without sexual transmissibility may be due to the Teratogenic effect of the mutagens. This is particularly true with respect to seedling variants. The occurrences of several induced mutants have been reported

but some of the induced mutations viz. Unifoliate and Multifoliate do not seem to have been reported earlier in induced population. It was interesting to note that some of the induced mutations like Unifoliate leaf mutant occurred in nature also.

Considerable amount of variability has been induced through the use of the two mutagens (γ - rays and EMS) separately and in combination. Plant-type mutants with very Dwarf habit, early flowering may be advantageously used in mixed cropping or in hybridisation programmes. The present investigations have demonstrated the potential usefulness of induced mutagenesis for specific improvement in Pigeon pea by reducing the maturity time and increasing the number of pods in the otherwise superior varieties.

The results of the present study are compatible with the conclusion that there are differences in Mutation spectrum among Mutagenic agents and Varieties. In addition, they also indicate that there might be differences in Mutation spectrum between the different dose levels and the different types of mutagen treatments. There were also indications that combination treatment increased Mutation frequency.

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